

FABRICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF IN-PLANE ALIGNED NANOTUBE COMPOSITES WITH MAGNETICALLY ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBE BUCKY PAPERS

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ABSTRACT: Controlled alignment of single-walled nanotubes (SWNTs) is critical for developing high performance structural and multifunctional nanocomposites. In this study, a new technical approach was developed by the authors to prepare bulk polymeric composites containing in-plane aligned nanotubes. Aligned nanotube buckypapers with a thickness of 15-30 μ m were produced by filtrating well-dispersed SWNT suspensions under high magnetic fields (15-25 Tesla). The area of the fabricated aligned buckypapers can be as large as 387cm² (60 in²) and the buckypapers have good strength and flexibility for handling during composite process. The aligned buckypapers can be used just like conventional fiber mats to achieve desirable reinforcement orientations. A special resin infiltration technique was also developed to facilitate tube/epoxy resin impregnation and to cure the multiple-layer resin-wetted aligned buckypaper into bulk solid composite samples. The significant alignment of nanotubes in the buckypapers was observed using the scanning electronic microscope (SEM). Composite samples with multiple layers of aligned buckypapers were fabricated. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) shows that the storage modulus of the unidirectional SWNT composite sample was as high as 40.5GPa. The SEM observations of the cross-section of the resultant composite also showed significant alignment of the nanotubes along the desired direction, which indicated the tube alignment in the magnetically aligned buckypaper was successfully transited into the solid nanocomposites.

KEY WORDS: Nanocomposite, Nanotube, Alignment, Mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

Due to their nanoscale dimension, extra-high surface area ratio and strong molecular interactions, SWNTs have the tendency to form ropes that aggregate together and therefore it is very difficult to directly manipulate large quality tubes to achieve desired alignment during nanocomposite processing [1-10]. Several efforts have been made to control tube alignment in composites. Ajayan and his colleagues observed tube alignment during cutting polymer/nanotube samples [11]. Stretch-induced alignment, which is mechanically stretching the SWNTs/PMMA composites at an elevated temperature of 90°C, has also been attempted [12, 13]. Nanotube alignment has been reportedly achieved through spinning or spooling a mixture of nanotubes/resin into fiber or strip forms, which is called flow-induced alignment. However, these methods were considered ineffective because only local and relatively low degree of orientation can be randomly achieved. Possible reasons for the inability of aligning tubes in composites are

high resin viscosity, tube aggregation and strong tube/polymer resin molecular interactions after resin/tube mixing.

In this research, an innovative technical approach is proposed to realize more uniform tube alignment in nanotube-reinforced composites by using magnetically aligned buckypapers and resin infiltration. First, aligned nanotube buckypapers with a thickness of 15-30 μm were produced by filtrating well-dispersed SWNT suspensions under high magnetic fields (17.3-25 Tesla). Then, the aligned buckypapers were impregnated using a specific resin infiltration technique. Finally, multiple layers of the wetted buckypapers were stacked together and hot pressed to fabricate bulk composite materials with the desired dimension and controlled tube alignment, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. In-plane SWNT alignment and dispersion in nanocomposites

MAGNETICALLY ALIGNED BUCKYPAPER

Magnetic Alignment of SWNT The literature review indicates that the molar susceptibilities for a (10, 10) SWNT (armchair) is $+85.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ emu (mol C)}^{-1}$ when parallel to B (magnetic vector), and $-21.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ emu (mol C)}^{-1}$ when perpendicular to B. Theoretical predictions show that for a (10, 10) SWNT with a length of 300nm, a magnetic field of 17.3-25 T can align SWNTs suspended in a very low viscous solution. Dr. Richard Smalley's team experimentally demonstrated the effectiveness of aligning SWNTs in buckypapers under high magnetic fields of greater than 8 T with the filtration method [14]. In this study, we used a 20 T magnetic field available at the National High Magnetic Field Laboratory (NHMFL), Tallahassee, FL to carry out the nanotube alignment experiments.

Preparation of Large Magnetically Aligned Buckypaper To align the SWNTs in the magnetic field, the suspension of SWNTs should be stable for a minimum of four to ten hours depending on the thickness of the buckypaper to be made. The SWNTs used in this study were BuckyPearlsTM, purified SWNT product from Carbon Nanotechnologies, Inc. (CNI), Houston, TX. A stable suspension of SWNTs was prepared by sonicating a mixture of SWNT/water with the selected surfactant. The suspension had a concentration of 10-100mg/L. The sonication time depended on the concentration of the suspension. The suspension was found to be stable for more than 24 hours at room temperature and low pressure; however, as the suspension concentration increased, the stability of the suspension decreased proportionally.

A custom-made filter system was designed to produce large buckypapers with magnetically aligned nanotubes. Figures 2 and 3 shows the central filtration membrane (white color) and the filter setup right before put into a high magnetic field at the NHMFL. Figure 4 shows the entire filter assembly put into the magnet bore during the experiments. Figure 5 shows that a magnetically aligned buckypaper as large as 387cm^2 (60in^2) was successfully produced with the 17.3 T magnetic field for 10 hours. The buckypaper has a thickness of $17.8\mu\text{m}$. Currently, it is the world's largest magnetically aligned buckypaper of purified SWNTs.

Figure 2. Central part of the filter

Figure 3. Filter setup at NHMFL

Figure 4. Magnet bore and filter assembly

Figure 5. 387cm² magnetically aligned assembly buckypaper

Characterization of Tube Alignment The SEM image of the surface of this large aligned buckypaper is shown in Figure 6. As a comparison, an image of a buckypaper with randomly oriented nanotubes (filtration of SWNT suspension with 0T magnetic field) is shown in Figure 7. In order to observe internal tube alignment of the buckypaper, a sample with the surface peeled off was prepared. The SEM observation of the sample is shown in Figure 8. These observations indicated the significant tube alignment was achieved in such a large buckypaper, which afford the possibility for fabricating bulk composite samples with the preformed aligned nanotubes. It also shows that there are nanoscale porous structures existing in the aligned buckypaper, which may lead to a difficulty in resin impregnation during composite manufacturing.

Figure 6. SWNT alignment of the large magnetically aligned buckypaper (X15, 000)

Figure 7. Surface of random buckypaper

Figure 8. Nanotube alignment on the peeled-off surface of the aligned buckypaper

NANOCOMPOSITES WITH IN-PLANE ALIGNED SWNT

Fabrication of Nanocomposites Wetting or impregnating buckypapers with epoxy resin is far more difficult than processing conventional fiber reinforced composites because of buckypaper's nanoscale porous structures and the intensive molecular interactions between SWNTs and resin molecules. The resin matrix used in this research was Epon 862/EPI-CURE W curing agent supplied by Shell Chemical Co. The resin's viscosity was as high as 2700cP at room temperature, preventing infiltration through the buckypapers along their thickness direction even under full vacuum. The thickness of the buckypaper was only 10-80 μ m. Only extra low viscosity resin solution could infiltrate through and wet the SWNT networks of the buckypapers. More than two hours were required for the diluted resin solution with a viscosity below 10cP to properly infiltrate through a 15 μ m thick buckypaper along the thickness direction. Multiple layers of the well impregnated buckypapers were stacked together and cured at 177 $^{\circ}$ C for two hours, then post-cured for an additional two hours at 177 $^{\circ}$ C to fabricate the final bulk solid composite

samples. The composite samples had diameters of 25-90mm and thickness of 40-200mm depending on the number of layers of impregnated buckypapers used. By using the large size aligned buckypaper and the resin infiltration method, a six-layer magnetically aligned buckypaper/epoxy composite sample was successfully produced, as shown in Figure 9. In the composite, all six aligned buckypapers were stacked along the same alignment direction. The heavy curvature of this composite sample is also a good indication of tube alignment, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Heavy curvature of magnetically aligned buckypaper composite

DMA Analysis of Aligned tube SWNT Composites Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was conducted to explore the mechanical properties of the resultant nanocomposites with in-plane aligned SWNTs. The SWNT content was as high as 59.8 wt.% during to the dense packing of the aligned tubes in the composites. Figure 10 shows the DMA testing result of the composite sample along the tube alignment direction. The storage modulus of the resultant nanocomposites is as high as 40.5GPa, which is one of the highest reported data available for both nanotube fiber and composites. The figure also shows that the random buckypaper composites of 31.3wt.% tube loading has a storage modulus of 15.1GPa, which is a 480% increase compared to 2.6GPa storage modulus of the neat resin.

Figure 10. DMA analysis of aligned and random SWNT composites

Nanostructural Characterization of the Aligned Buckypaper Composites The cross-section of the aligned buckypaper composites is shown in Figure 11. It can be seen that the resin/tube has

a good impregnation throughout the cross-section in the nanocomposites. Figure 12 shows that the nanotubes had a very good alignment in the nanocomposites, which indicated that the tube alignment in the magnetically aligned buckypaper was successfully transited into bulk solid composite samples.

(X700)

Figure 11. Cross-section of the aligned buckypaper composite

(X12, 000)

Figure 12. Tube alignment in the composite

CONCLUSIONS

In this research, the world's largest magnetically aligned buckypapers were successfully produced with high magnetic fields at the NHMFL. The aligned buckypaper was as large as 387cm² (60in²) with a thickness around 20μm. Significant tube alignment was observed in the aligned buckypaper. A special resin infiltration technique was developed to fabricate bulk composite samples with controlled in-plane tube orientation. The storage modulus of the resultant aligned composites was as high as 40.5GPa. Good tube alignment was also observed in the composites, which indicated that the tube alignment in the magnetically aligned buckypaper was successfully transited into bulk solid composite samples. The research results show that the integrated magnetically aligned buckypapers and resin infiltration technique is an effective method to produce bulk nanocomposite materials with controlled in-plane SWNT alignment.

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